

Heterocycles Fused with the 3,4-Bond of 1-Benzopyran : Synthesis from the Compounds other than 1-Benzopyrans

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A review on the synthesis of the title type of heterocycles from the compounds other than 1-benzopyrans covering the literature through volume 110 of *Chemical Abstracts* is presented.

FUSED heterocycles of the title type may be generally represented by the figure (A), the letters B, P and H inscribed in the assemblance (A) denoting respectively the benzene, pyran and X heteroatom containing heterocyclic rings. The ring size of the heterocycle (H) as well as the bond with respect to the heteroatom (X) through which it gets fused with the pyran, may vary. Again, this heterocycle (H) may

be a monocyclic one or a part of a polycyclic system and may contain more than one like or unlike heteroatom. The carbon corresponding to C-2 of [1]benzopyran, which is not in fusion with any ring in the system (A), may be optionally functionalised. The four general modes of construction of the heterocyclic system (A) are: (i) formation of the heterocyclic (H) ring over the preformed benzopyran (BP) ring, i.e. BP→BPH procedure, (ii) reaction of a heterocyclic compound with a suitable benzene derivative to form benzene having a heterocyclic moiety as a substituent (B-H system) which is subsequently converted to the BPH system, i.e. B+H→B-H→BPH procedure, (iii) reaction of several benzene derivatives with some carbocyclic or acyclic compounds forming the BPH system with or without the intermediacy of the B-H system, i.e. B→BPH procedure, and (iv) reaction of a benzheterocycle with reagents other than benzene derivatives, i.e. BH→BPH procedure.

The other possible PH→BPH mode (construction of the benzene ring over the preformed PH ring) is

not yet explored. A review on the synthesis of the system (A) from [1]benzopyran derivatives, i.e. by the general construction mode (i) has appeared very recently from this laboratory¹. The present review, complementary to the earlier one¹, gives a comprehensive survey on the synthesis of the title heterocycles illustrating the three other modes of construction of the system and covers the literature through volume 110 of *Chemical Abstracts* (i.e. upto June 1989). The projected survey is recorded here in the following sections based on the size of the heterocyclic (H) ring and the nature of the heteroatom contained therein, some of the sections being further divided into subsections depending on the nature of the key synthons. The patented works concerning the synthesis of the system (A) are rarely cited. The fused heterocycles of the type (B) in which the 3,4-bond of the pyran moiety is in fusion with the carbocyclic part of another heterocycle and the various reactions of the preformed system (A) are not included in this review. While describing the synthesis of the coumarino fused heterocycles (A; R¹R²=O), the publications comprehended in an earlier review² and the formation of the system by lactonisation of the compounds of the type (C) are least emphasised. The methods described here for the synthesis of the system (A) unsubstituted at the benzene (B) ring are generally applicable to that having alkyl, alkoxy, halogeno and many other substituents at the benzene ring.

Five-membered ring containing one nitrogen atom

From the reaction of heterocyclic compounds with the appropriate benzene derivatives

The lactam 1 (X=H; R=Me, PhCH₂; n=1) is acylated by 2-hydroxybenzoic ester; the acylated product 1 (X=COC₆H₄OH-*o*; R=Me, PhCH₂; n=1) on heating over its melting point gives the pyrroline 2 (n=1) that is dehydrogenated by DDQ to the pyrrole 3 (X=NR; Y=bond; R¹R²=O; R³=R⁴=H)³. *N*-Alkylpyridinium bromide, prepared from 2-ethylpyridine and 2-hydroxy-5-methylphenacyl bromide, on ring closure followed by condensation with Ar₂CO (Ar=C₆H₅R-*p*; R=H, OMe,

NMe₂) affords the fused indolizine **4** (X=CMe; R¹=R²=Ar)⁴. Pechmann condensation of the β-ketoester **5** (X=NH) with resorcinol gives the indole **6** (X=NH)⁵.

From the derivatives of 2-allyloxy- and 2-propargyloxybenzaldehydes

From imines corresponding to 2-allyloxy- and 2-propargyloxybenzaldehydes: Synthesis of pyrrolo[3,2-c][1]benzopyrans by intramolecular 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition via azomethine or azallyl anion of several imines corresponding to the aldehydes **7** (X=O; R¹=R²=H; R³=Ph) and **7** (X=O; R¹R²=bond; R³=H, Ph) has been extensively exploited. Thus, the imine **7** (X=NCHPhCO₂Me; R¹R²=bond; R³=H) initially undergoes thermal cyclisation to **8** (R¹R²=bond; R³=R⁶=R⁷=H; R⁴=CO₂Me; R⁵=Ph) followed by thermal dehydrogenation with concurrent migration of methoxycarbonyl group giving ultimately the pyrrole **3** (X=NH; Y=bond; R¹=R²=H; R³=CO₂Me; R⁴=Ph)⁶; a naphthalene analog of the aforementioned toward's heat treatment⁷. The glycinate **7** (X=NCHPhCO₂Me; R¹=R²=H; R³=Ph) in refluxing xylene produces an isomeric mixture of the pyrrolidines **8** (R¹=β-H; R²=R⁶=R⁷=H; R³=R⁵=Ph; R⁴=CO₂Me), **8** (R¹=β-H; R²=R⁶=R⁷=H; R³=R⁴=Ph; R⁵=CO₂Me), and **8** (R¹=α-H; R²=R⁶=R⁷=H; R³=R⁵=Ph; R⁴=CO₂Me)⁸. A naphthalene analog of the glycinate **7** (X=NCHPhCO₂Me; R¹=R³=H) also thermally cyclises to a stereoisomeric mixture of the *cis*-fused pyrrolidines corresponding to the naphthalene analog of **8** (R¹=β-H; R²=R³=R⁶=R⁷=H; R³, R⁴=Ph, CO₂Me)⁷. The imine **7** (X=NCHPhCO₂Me; R¹R²=OCH=CH; R³=H), derived from 2-(2-furylmethyloxy)-benzaldehyde and methyl phenylglycinate, cyclises thermally to the stereoisomeric mixture of **8** (R¹R²=β-OCH=CH; R³=R⁶=R⁷=H; R⁴, R⁵=CO₂Me, Ph)⁹. At a later date Arms-

trong *et al.*¹⁰ thoroughly studied the aforementioned cycloaddition reaction and observed that stereomutation at C(2) in the product **8** occurs in the case of imines either derived from phenylglycine methyl ester or having an unactivated dipolarophile. Intramolecular 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of **7** (X=NCHPhCN; R¹R²=bond; R³=H or Ph) is accompanied by dehydrocyanation so as to produce the pyrrole **3** (X=NH; Y=bond; R¹=R²=H; R³=H or Ph; R⁴=Ph), this product being also similarly formed from **7** [C(CN)=CHPh in place of CHX; R¹R²=bond; R³=H or Ph]¹¹. The intramolecular cycloadduct of the allyloxyimine **7** (X=NCHPhCN; R¹=R²=H; R³=H or Me) also dehydrocyanates spontaneously to form **8** (R¹=β-H; R²=R⁷=H; R³=H or Me; R⁴=Ph; R⁵R⁶=bond)¹¹. The perhydropyrrolobenzopyran **8** (R¹=α-H; R²=R⁵=Ph; R³=R⁴=R⁶=R⁷=H) together with a 2,3-dihydrofuran is formed by anionic cyclisation of **7** (X=NCH₂Ph; R¹=R²=H; R³=Ph), similar results also being obtained from **7** (X=NCHMe₂; R¹=R²=H; R³=Ph)¹².

From the nitrones derived from 2-allyloxy- and 2-propargyloxybenzaldehydes: Interesting examples for inter- and intramolecular double 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition from nitrones derived from 2-allyloxybenzaldehyde have been reported by Tsuge *et al.*¹³.

The nitron **7** [X=N⁺(Me)O⁻; R¹=R²=H; R³=Me) undergoes intermolecular 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition to dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate (DMAD) at room temperature; the azomethine ylide generated from the resultant adduct **9** via its rearrangement to the corresponding aziridine simply on refluxing in toluene undergoes intramolecular [3+2]cycloaddition giving a stereo-isomeric mixture of **8** (R¹=β-H; R²=R⁷=H; R³=R⁶=Me; R⁴, R⁵=CO₂Me, COCO₂Me)¹³. The nitron **7** [X=N⁺(Me)O⁻; R¹R³=OCH=CH; R²=H) on similar treatment with DMAD forms a mixture of **8** (R¹R³=β-OCH=CH; R²=R⁷=H; R⁶=Me; R⁴, R⁵=COMe, COCO₂Me)¹³. Intramolecular cycloaddition also occurs smoothly even when the positions of the dipole and dipolarophile in the previously described nitrones are interchanged. Thus, the nitron derived from the aldehyde **10** (R¹=H, CO₂Et) and MeNH₂ cyclises to the pyrrolidine **11** (X=O; R¹=H, CO₂Et; R²=H); the product **11** (X=O; R¹=CO₂Et; R²=H) on reduction with LiAlH₄ followed by tosylation and catalytic hydrogenation furnishes **11** (X=CH₂; R¹=H; R²=OH)¹⁴.

From the O-allyl and O-acyl derivatives of salicylamide

The nitrile ylids generated *in situ* from the benzamides **12** (X=O; R¹-R³=H; R⁴=CH₂Ar) and **12** (X=O; R¹R²=bond; R³=H, Me; R⁴=CH₂Ar) by sequential treatment with SOCl₂ and NEt₃ undergo intra-molecular 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition to give the pyrrolo[3,2-c][1]benzopyran derivatives^{15,16}. The formation of the pyrrolopyran **3** (X=NMe; Y=bond; R¹-R³=H; R⁴=H, Me, Ph) by warming a benzene solution of the benzamide **12**

(X=O; R¹R²=bond; R³=H; MeNCHRCO₂H in place of NHR⁴; R=H, Me, Ph) with Ac₂O involves an intramolecular cycloaddition of the mesoionic oxazolium-5-olate intermediate (13) followed by CO₂ extrusion¹⁷.

From 2-(2-allyloxyphenyl)oxazaphosphole

Thermolysis or photolysis of 2-(2-allyloxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-3,3-di-(trifluoromethyl)-5,5,5-trimethoxy-1,3,5, λ⁶-oxazaphosphole generates a 1,3-dipole that undergoes intramolecular cycloaddition to furnish the pyrroline **8** (R¹-R³=H; R⁴=R⁵=CF₃; R⁶R⁷=bond)¹⁸.

From other benzene derivatives

ω-Bromoacetophenone on sequential treatment with PhCH₂NHCH₂CH₂CN, NaBH₄, and NaN(TMS)₂ forms *trans*-1-benzyl-3-cyano-4-phenylpyrrolidine that is cyclised (polyphosphoric acid or P₂O₅ in MeSO₃H) to **14** (R=CH₂Ph); PhOCOCl converts **14** (R=CH₂Ph) to **14** (R=COOPh) that on Baeyer-Villiger oxidation produces **15** (X=Z=CH₂; Y=NCOOPh; R=α-H; R¹R²=O)¹⁸.

Five-membered ring containing more than one nitrogen atom

From the reaction of heterocyclic compounds with the appropriate benzene derivatives

2-(2-Hydroxy-5-methylphenyl)-1-azaindolizine, prepared from either 2-amino- or 2-methylpyridine,

on condensation with Michler's hydrol followed by oxidation with K₃Fe(CN)₆ gives [1]benzopyrano-[4',3':3,4]pyrazolo[1,5-a]pyridine **4** (X=N; R¹=R²=N,N-dimethylaminophenyl)⁴. Several compounds belonging to this system are useful in the dye industry and these have been patented¹⁹. Similar condensation of 2-dialkylamino-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)thiazole with 4,4'-bis(dialkylamino)benzohydrol followed by oxidation with K₃Fe(CN)₆ results the heterocycle **16** (R¹-R⁴=alkyl)¹⁹.

Formation by the B→BPH procedure

The azine **17** (R¹=R²=H; R³=H, Me; R⁴R⁵=CH=CH-CH=CH), obtained from the appropriate 2-allyloxynaphthalene-1-carboxaldehyde and hydrazine, on thermolysis (heating to 200° in PhNMe₂) undergoes intramolecular bis[3+2]cycloaddition to give the *cis*-fused heterocycle **18** (R¹-R⁶ as before). On the contrary, the azine **17** (R¹=R²=R⁴=R⁵=H; R³=H, Me) on similar thermolysis undergoes exclusively Claisen rearrangement. Both the azines **17** (R¹R²=bond; R³=H; R⁴R⁵=CH=CH-CH=CH) and **17** (R¹R²=bond; R³-R⁶=H), however, behave similarly on thermolysis yielding the heterocycles **18** (R¹-R⁶ as before)²⁰. Tosylhydrazone **7** (X=NNHTs; R¹-R²=H; R³=H, Ph) on treatment with NaOMe in darkness produces via the corresponding (2-allyloxyphenyl)diazomethane the fairly stable 1-pyrazoline **19** (R¹=R²=R⁶=H; R³=H, Ph; R⁴R⁵=bond)²¹. The hydrazone **7** (X=NNHTs; R¹=R³=H) couples with phenyldiazonium chloride; the resultant 5-(2-allyloxyphenyl)-2-phenyltetrazole on heating as well as irradiation gives via a nitrilimine intermediate the pyrazoline **19** (R¹-R³=H; R⁴=Ph; R⁵R⁶=bond) that can be dehydrogenated by chloranil to **19** (R¹R²=R⁵R⁶=bond; R³=H; R⁴=Ph)²². Arylsulphonylhydrazone **7** (X=NNHSO₂Ar; R¹=R²=H; R³=H, Me, Ph, CN) on treatment with Pb(OAc)₄ gives a nitrilimine intermediate that cyclises to **19** (R¹=R²=H; R⁴=SO₂Ar; R⁵R⁶=bond), alkali bringing about its hydrolysis and air-oxidation to **19** (R¹R²=R⁵R⁶=bond; R⁴=H)²³. The arylhydrazone **7** (X=NNHAr; R¹R²=bond; R³=H, Ar¹) undergoes cycloaddition via its 1,3-dipolar azomethine imine tautomer, the initial cycloadduct often being dehydrogenated under the reaction conditions. Pb(OAc)₄ converts the hydrazone **7** (X=NNHAr; R¹=R²=H; R³=Ar¹) to **19** (R¹=R²=R⁵=R⁶=H; R³=Ar¹; R⁴=Ar) which is often dehydrogenated in the presence of excess Pb(OAc)₄²⁴. 3-Substituted-2-aryl-1,2,3,3a,4,9a-hexahydro[1]benzopyrano[4,3-c]pyrazole hydrochloride is considered as an intramolecular [3⁺+2] cycloadduct of the aldehyde **7** (X=O; R¹=R²=H; R³=Me, Ph, CN, CO₂Et) and an arylhydrazine hydrochloride²⁵. Analogous cycloadduct is also formed from 2-allyloxyacetophenone and arylhydrazine hydrochloride²⁵. The formation of **19** (R¹=R²=R³=R⁶=H; R⁴=COR; R⁵=Me) and **19** (R¹R²=bond; R³=H or CH₂OH; R⁴=COR; R⁵=Me; R⁶=H) by reacting the aldehydes **7** (X=O; R¹-R³=H) and **7** (X=O; R¹R²=bond; R³=H or CH₂OH) respectively,

with MeNHNHCOR (R=Me or Ph) also occurs via the azomethine imine intermediates³⁶.

2-Hydroxybenzoxazole on treatment with NaN₃—NH₄Cl in DMF followed by MeI gives 5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-2-methyltetrazole, the allyl and propargyl ethers of which on irradiation give respectively the fused pyrazoline **19** (R¹—R³=H; R⁴=Me; R⁵R⁶=bond) and pyrazole **19** (R¹R²=R⁵R⁶=bond; R³=H; R⁴=Me)²⁷. The arylhydrazides of 2-allyloxy- and 2-propargyloxybenzoic acid on sequential treatment with SOCl₂ and NEt₃ give the pyrazoline **19** (R¹—R³=H; R⁴=Ar; R⁵R⁶=bond)^{25,27,28} and pyrazole **19** (R¹R²=R⁵R⁶=bond; R³=H; R⁴=Ar)²⁸ respectively.

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22

Five-membered ring containing one oxygen or sulphur atom

The β -ketoester **5** (X=O) condenses with resorcinol giving **6** (X=O)⁵. Claisen rearrangement of 1,4-diphenoxybut-2-yne to a mixture of *cis*-benzofuro[3,2-*c*][1]benzopyran **15** (X=O; YZ=benzo; R= α -Me; R¹=R³=H) and a benzofuro[3,2-*b*]benzofuran derivative²⁹ has given a fillip to study the rearrangement of several other 1,4-diaryloxybut-2-yne under different conditions^{30,31}. Claisen re-

arrangement of 1,4-bis(*m*-methoxyphenoxy)-2-butyne is not regioselective, the two [3,3]sigmatropic shifts only occurring preferentially to the *para*-positions of the methoxy substituents³². The betaine **20** (Y=bond; R=CH=CH₂), prepared by treating the thioanilide **12** (X=S; R=Ph; R¹—R³=H) with PhCHBrCOCl—NEt₃, undergoes intramolecular 1,4-cycloaddition giving the *endo*-isomer **21** (Y=bond; Z=CH; R¹=R²=H) together with a small amount of the *exo*-isomer **22** (Y, Z, R¹, R² as before)³³. The betaine **20** (Y=bond; R=C≡CH), prepared by treating **12** (X=S; R=Ph; R¹R²=bond; R³=H) with PhCHBrCOCl—NEt₃ similarly gives the cycloadduct **22** (Y=bond; Z=CH; R¹R²=bond) which on thermal elimination of PhNCO furnishes the thiophene **3** (X=S, Y=bond; R¹—R³=H; R⁴=Ph)³³.

Five-membered rings containing two unlike heteroatoms

These are generally prepared from certain benzene derivatives with or without the intermediacy of the B—H system.

The nitron obtained by addition of MeNH₂OH to the *trans*-olefin **7** (X=O; R¹=H; R³=H, Me, Ph, CO₂Me, CH₂Cl) undergoes stereospecific cycloaddition to give the *cis*-fused [1]benzopyrano[4,3-*c*]isoxazole **23** (R¹= β -H; R²=R⁵=H; R⁴=Me)^{34,35}. The orientation of this and several allied cycloadditions have been interpreted in terms of FMO theory³⁶. The dehydration of 2-allyloxybenzaldoxime **7** (X=NOH; R¹—R³=H) and 2-propynyloxybenzaldoxime **7** (X=NOH; R¹R²=bond; R³=H) leads respectively to isoxazoline **23** (R¹—R³=H; R⁴R⁵=bond) and isoxazole **23** (R¹R²=R⁴R⁵=bond; R³=H) presumably via the nitrile oxide intermediates³⁷. The formation of fused isoxazolines of the type **23** via the nitron intermediates by reacting some 2(2-allyloxyphenyl)substituted alkynes with appropriate hydroxylamine has been reported by Padwa and Wong³⁸. Thus, from the reaction of PhNH₂OH with methyl β -(allyloxyphenyl)propargylate is isolated the isoxazoline **23** (R¹= β -H; R²=R³=H; R⁴=Ph; R⁵=CH₂CO₂Me). In refluxing aqueous ethanolic solution, MeNH₂OH also undergoes 1,4-addition to 4-(2-allyloxyphenyl)but-3-yn-2-one; the resultant *cis-trans* mixture of the adducts on boiling in benzene affords **23** (R¹= β -H; R²=R³=H; R⁴=Me; R⁵=CH₂COMe). Even (2-allyloxyphenyl)acetylene reacts with MeNH₂OH giving **23** (R¹= β -H; R²=R³=H; R⁴=R⁵=Me) via the same nitron intermediate as arising from the reaction of 2-allyloxyacetophenone with MeNH₂OH³⁸.

4-Acetyl-3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-5-isoxazolinone, prepared by reacting ω -carbethoxy-*o*-methoxyacetophenone with NH₂OH followed by acylation with MeC(OEt)₃, cyclises to the [1]benzopyrano[4,3-*c*]isoxazol-3-one on treatment with AlCl₃ in benzene³⁹. The betaine **20** (Y=bond; R=CN), prepared by treating 2-(cyanomethoxy)benzanilide with PhCHBrCOCl—NEt₃, gives the cycloadduct **22** (Y=R¹R²=bond; Z=N) which on thermal elimination of PhNCO furnishes 2-phenyl-4*H*-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-*d*]thia-

zole³³. Oxathiazolone **24**, prepared by reacting salicylamide with ClC(O)SCl , can be acylated by $\text{PhC}\equiv\text{CCOCl}$ and $\text{PhCH}=\text{CHCOCl}$ to **25** and **26** respectively. When refluxed in xylene, **25** affords the coumarinoisothiazole **27** ($\text{X}=\text{N}$; $\text{Y}=\text{S}$; $\text{Z}=\text{CPh}$; $\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$)⁴⁰. Under similar conditions, **26** also gives the above isothiazole together with a chromenoquinoline **27** ($\text{X}=\text{N}$; $\text{Y}=\text{benzo}$; $\text{Z}=\text{CH}$; $\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$) and some other chromone byproducts⁴⁰.

Six-membered ring containing one nitrogen atom

From reaction of heterocyclic compounds with the appropriate benzene derivatives

1-Phenoxypyridinium fluoroborate, prepared from methyl nicotinate-1-oxide and phenyldiazonium tetrafluoroborate, undergoes base-catalysed rearrangement to methyl (2-hydroxyphenyl)nicotinate that ultimately lactonises to **28** ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$; $\text{R}^3-\text{R}^5=\text{H}$)⁴¹. The acyllactam **1** ($\text{X}=\text{COC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH-}o$; $\text{R}=\text{Me}$, PhCH_2 ; $n=2$) on heating with pyridine hydrochloride gives **2** ($\text{R}=\text{H}$; $n=2$) that on dehydrogenation affords the pyridine **28** ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$; $\text{R}^3-\text{R}^5=\text{H}$)³. ϵ -Keto- ϵ -caprolactam on treatment with PhONH_2 . HCl followed by refluxing in $\text{Me}_2\text{CHOH-EtOH}$ containing HCl affords 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-5-oxo-5H-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-*b*]pyridine⁴². Isatin on condensation with *o*-methoxyphenylacetic acid followed by demethylation and lactonisation affords **29** ($\text{XY}=\text{CONH}$; $\text{Z}=\text{C}$; $\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$; $\text{R}^3\text{R}^4=\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}$)⁴³.

23

24, $\text{R}=\text{H}$
25, $\text{R}=\text{COC}\equiv\text{CPh}$
26, $\text{R}=\text{E}-\text{COCH}=\text{CHPh}$

27

28

29

30

31

1-Substituted-2-carbethoxypiperidin-3-one, 3-carbethoxypiperidin-4-one, and 4-carbethoxypiperidin-

3-one on acid-catalysed condensation with the appropriately substituted phenol or resorcinol give respectively the compounds of the types **30** ($\text{XR}^5=\text{YR}^4=\text{CH}_2$; $\text{ZR}^3=\text{N-alkyl}$; $\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$), **30** ($\text{XR}^5=\text{ZR}^3=\text{CH}_2$; $\text{YR}^4=\text{N-alkyl}$; $\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$), and **30** ($\text{XR}^5=\text{N-alkyl}$; $\text{YR}^4=\text{ZR}^3=\text{CH}_2$; $\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$)⁴⁴; many compounds belonging to the latter two types and their MeMgI addition products possess psychotropic and analgesic properties, and they have been patented. Cyclisation of 2-chloro-3-(phenoxymethyl)quinoline in DMF containing NaH to the quinoline **28** ($\text{R}^1-\text{R}^3=\text{H}$; $\text{R}^4\text{R}^5=\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}$) has been reported very recently⁴⁵. 1,4-Dihydro-2,6-dimethyl-3,5-diethoxycarbonyl-4-(2-methoxy-5-nitrophenyl)pyridine⁴⁶ on treatment with BBr_3 in CH_2Cl_2 forms 3,10*b*-dihydro-2,4-dimethyl-1-methoxycarbonyl-9-nitro-5*H*-5-oxo[1]benzopyrano[3,4-*c*]pyridine⁴⁷.

Formation by the B→BPH procedure

2-(*N*-Methyliminomethyl)anisole on condensation with glutaric anhydride gives *trans*-1-methyl-5-carboxy-6-(2-methoxyphenyl)-2-piperidone that on *O*-demethylation and cyclodehydration results the *trans*-fused piperidone **15** ($\text{X}=\text{NMe}$; $\text{Y}=\text{CO}$; $\text{Z}=\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$; $\text{R}=\beta\text{-H}$; $\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$)⁴⁸. Similarly, *trans*-1-methyl-5-carboxy-6-(2,6-dimethoxy-4-*n*-amylphenyl)-2-piperidone, prepared from 2,6-dimethoxy-4-*n*-amylbenzylidene-methylamine and glutaric anhydride, has been converted to the nitrogen analog of $\Delta^1(6)$ -*trans*-tetrahydrocannabinol⁴⁹. 2-Amino-2'-fluorobenzophenone is cyclised with ethyl acetoacetate to give ethyl 4-(2-fluorophenyl)-2-methylquinoline-3-carboxylate which on reduction with LiAlH_4 and cyclisation with NaH gives the pyridine **31** ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{H}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}^4\text{R}^5=\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}$)⁵⁰. Synthesis of a pyridine of the type **31** ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{NH}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{NH}_2$; $\text{R}^4=\text{Ph}$; $\text{R}^5=\text{H}$) by heating together a 2'-hydroxychalcone, $\text{CH}_2(\text{CN})_2$, and NH_4OAc in EtOH has been achieved⁵¹. The chromanoniminium salt **32**, not accessible from the corresponding chromanone but prepared by heating 3,4-dimethoxyphenol, acrylonitrile, and sodium together in ether followed by saturation of the solution with dry HCl, undergoes self-condensation with elimination of NH_3 in the presence of Na_2CO_3 to give the pyridine **28** ($\text{R}^1-\text{R}^4=\text{H}$; $\text{R}^5=2$ -hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl)⁵². The pyridine **31** ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{R}^4=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}^5=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) has been prepared by condensing salicylaldehyde with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of NH_4OAc ⁵³. One molecule of salicylaldehyde reacts with two molecules of methyl 3-aminocrotonate in AcOH forming the pyridine **31** ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{R}^4=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}^5=\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$)⁵⁴. The aldol condensate of salicylaldehyde and indanone on condensation with $\text{NCCH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ in the presence of NH_4OAc followed by acid hydrolysis yields the pyridone **31** ($\text{R}^1\text{R}^2=\text{O}$; $\text{R}^3=\text{OH}$; $\text{R}^4\text{R}^5=1,2$ -indeno; amide form)⁵⁵.

Intramolecular 1,4-dipolar cycloaddition of the betaine **20** ($\text{Y}=\text{CO}$; $\text{R}=\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), prepared from **12** ($\text{X}=\text{S}$; $\text{R}=\text{Ph}$; $\text{R}^1\text{R}^3=\text{H}$) and $\text{PhC}(\text{COCl})=\text{C}=\text{O}$, in refluxing toluene furnishes the cycloadduct

22 ($Y=CO$; $Z=CH$; $R^1=R^2=H$)⁶⁶. Similar treatment of **20** ($Y=CO$; $R=C\equiv CH$) gives the pyridone **29** ($X=NPh$; $Y=CO$; $Z=C$; $R^1-R^3=H$; $R^4=Ph$) through thermal elimination of COS from the intermediate cycloadduct⁶⁶. The formation of the quinoline **27** ($X=N$; $Y=benzo$; $Z=CH$; $R^1=R^2=H$) by treating 2-propargyloxybenzanilide with $POCl_3$ is postulated to involve a nitrilium attack on the triple bond⁶⁷. Photolysis of 3-(2-allyloxyphenyl)-2*H*-azirine generates a 1,3-dipole that undergoes intramolecular cycloaddition to furnish 2,3,4,4a-dihydro-5*H*-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-*b*]pyridine^{1 6}.

Six-membered rings with more than one nitrogen atom

From the hydrazone of 2-propargyloxybenzaldehyde

The hydrazone **7** ($X=NNHAr$; $R^1R^2=bond$; $R^3=CN$ or CO_2Et) undergoes intramolecular ene reaction to give the arylhydrazone of 4-chromanone that ultimately cyclises to a pyridazine derivative fused with the 3,4-bond of [1]benzopyran^{7,68}.

Formation by the BH→BPH and B-H→BPH modes of construction

Thermal condensation of benzofuran with 3,6-dimethoxycarbonyl-*sym*-tetrazine furnishes 2-methoxycarbonyl-5*H*-5-oxo-[1]benzopyrano[3,4-*c*]pyridazine **3** ($X=bond$; $Y=N=N$; $R^1R^2=O$; $R^3=CO_2Me$; $R^4=H$)⁶⁹. Benzoxazinylidenemalononitrile **33** on refluxing with NH_4OAc in $MeOCH_2-CH_2OH$ gives 4-amino-5-imino-2-phenyl-5*H*-1-benzopyrano[4,3-*d*]pyrimidine⁶⁰. It has been observed very recently that the malononitrile **33** (2- HOC_6H_4 in place of Ph) as well as 4-[cyano(ethoxycarbonyl)-methylene]-2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-4*H*-1,3-benzoxazine reacts with NH_4OAc and H_2S or an aqueous acid giving 4,5-(imino, thioxo or oxo)-disubstituted-2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-5*H*-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-*d*]pyrimidines⁶¹.

The cyanomethyl ether **35** of the 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,4-triazine **34** ($R^1, R^2=Aryl$), prepared by three component condensation of salicylhydrazide, diaryl-1,2-diketone and NH_4OAc , on heating at 240° undergoes intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction (nitrile group functioning as the dienophile) with concomitant nitrogen extrusion to yield 2,3-diaryl-5*H*-1-benzopyrano[3,4-*b*]pyrazine **36** ($R^1, R^2=Aryl$)⁶².

Six-membered ring containing one oxygen or sulphur atom

From the reaction of heterocyclic compounds with the appropriate benzene derivatives

Von Pechman condensation of the β -ketoester **37** ($R^3, R^5=alkyl$) with resorcinol gives the pyran **30** ($X=Z=CH$; $YR^4=O$; $R^6=H$; $R^7=OH$)⁶³. Thiazolin-2-one-4-thione and thiazolin-2, 4-dithione have been condensed with salicylaldehyde and the resultant condensates subjected to Diels-Alder reaction with ethyl acrylate to produce **38** ($X=O$)⁶⁴ and **38** ($X=S$)⁶⁵, respectively.

From the aldol condensates of 2-allyloxybenzaldehyde by intramolecular hetero Diels-Alder cyclisation

The aldehyde **7** ($X=O$; $R^1=H$; $R^2=R^3=Me$) reacts with the dioxane **39** ($X=Z=O$; $Y=CMe_2$; $Q=bond$) to give the aldol intermediate which undergoes intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction to give **40**. The aldehyde **7** ($X=O$; $R^1-R^3=H$) reacts with the pyrimidine **39** ($X=Z=NMe$; $Y=CO$; $Q=bond$) to give a mixture of **40** and **41** while **7** ($X=O$; $R^1=Me$; $R^2=R^3=H$) with the same pyrimidine gives only **41** ($R^1=Me$) showing substituent effect on the intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction⁶⁶. *Trans*-2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7-hexahydro-3,4-dimethyl-2-phenyl-1,4-oxazepine-5,7-dione **39** ($X=NMe$; $Y=CHMe$; $Z=CHPh$; $Q=O$) condenses with **7** ($X=O$; $R^1=H$; $R^2=R^3=Me$); the resultant condensate undergoes stereoselective hetero Diels-Alder cyclisation in $ClCH_2Cl$ containing Et_2AlCl giving mainly **40**, this cycloadduct undergoing acid-catalysed hydrolysis to **15** ($XYZ=CH_2-COOCMe_2$; $R=\alpha-H$; $R^1=R^2=H$)⁶⁷. The α,β -unsaturated ketone obtained by aldol condensation of **7** ($X=O$; $R^1=H$; $R^2=R^3=Me$) and 1-unsubstituted or 1-alkyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one, cyclises to **40** [$XYZ=C(Me)=N$; $Q=NR$; $R=H, alkyl$; $R^1=H$; $R^2=R^3=Me$]⁶⁸.

From other benzene derivatives

Treatment of $CH_2(COC_6H_4OH-o)_2$ with CS_2 and Me_2SO_4 in the presence of KOH gives a chromonochromone that rearranges on heating with aqueous HOAc to the coumarinochromone **3** ($X=O$; $Y=CO$; $R^1R^2=O$; $R^3R^4=CH=CH-CH=CH$)⁶⁹. Formation of [1]benzopyrano[4,3-*c*][1]benzopyran derivative **42** by treating 2-hydroxystilbene with Ag_2O or DDQ is highly interesting⁷⁰.

Seven-membered rings containing one or more than one heteroatom

2,3-Dihydro-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,5-benzoxa (or benzthia)zepine, prepared from 2-HOC₆H₄COCH₂-CH₂NMe₂ and 2-hydroxy (or mercapto)aniline, reacts with the anhydride RCOOAc (R=alkyl or aryl) to yield **43** [X=O (or S)]⁷¹; analogously, 2,3-dihydro-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,5-benzdiazepine with Ac₂O gives **43** (X=NH; R=Me)⁷¹.

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